

Senior High School Students' Assessment of Academic Support on Modular Distance Learning During COVID-19

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ABSTRACT: Modular Distance Learning (MDL) is a way of learning in the Philippines' basic education that allows students to access printed self-learning modules (SLM) and modules that can be accessed digitally or via electronic devices such as laptops, computers, tablets, and smartphones. The purpose of this study was to determine how senior high school students perceive academic support in modular distance learning. It was conducted for two months in two senior high schools in one of the districts in the Division of Misamis Oriental and had fifty respondents. This study was descriptive in nature involving quantitative analyses. Purposive sampling was used in identifying the senior high school students. The instrument used was a demographic profiling questionnaire and a self-made 20-item survey questionnaire. Four master teachers and two principals validated it. In determining the significant difference, ANOVA was utilized as a statistical treatment. Findings revealed that most student-respondents were enrolled in Technical Vocational Track and belonged to the low-income class. Additionally, when students were grouped according to their demographic profile, their assessment of academic support indicated a significant difference in the support they received from teachers and peers but no difference in the academic support they received from technical and parental sources. Teachers, parents, and administrators all contribute significantly to the students' learning process. Academic support is only possible when administrators, teachers, parents, and members of the community work together effectively.

KEYWORDS: academic support, learning space, modular distance learning, most essential learning competencies, senior high school assessment

I. INTRODUCTION

The pandemic brought by COVID-19 had caused a catastrophic change in many aspects of life and education is not excused from it. The education system has drastically altered from conventional face-to-face classes to a new dimension in the school year 2020-2021. The new normal setup of education has been adopted not just by the teachers, but also by the students and the parents. This setup was made to control the spread of the virus and contract it. On the UNESCO Institute for Statistics Database (2020) report, COVID-19 has barged into classroom learning and 9 out of 10 students in private and public institutions worldwide were greatly affected. This number excludes teachers, parents, and other school faculty members from being counted as one of the people who were affected by distance learning. As of September 13, 2021, there were 2,251,346 active cases affected by the virus and 35,312 deaths in the Philippines, according to the current statistics of Johns Hopkins University (Johns Hopkins University 2021). Despite contracting the virus by closing the schools in that particular school year to most countries, the figures had still increased.

According to a national news report, about 22 million public school students in the Philippines set out for distance learning in the year 2020 (Bernardo, 2020). The education system in the Philippines started implementing modular and online distance learning in the year 2020 up to the current school year. The students

are in their second year for their distance learning. School closure has affected millions of Filipino learners. This affects their learning process and their social skills development since they are just learning inside their respective houses with the guidance of their learning delivery modalities. World Bank even stated that students affected by closing the schools have reduced 10% of their potential lifetime learning.

On December 2021, about 170 schools in the country started the pilot testing for the face-to-face classes in coordination with the Department of Health and respective Local Government Units (Malipot, 2021). Public and private schools in the Philippines, especially basic education, were not yet opened for conventional face-to-face classes. So, students still rely on distance learning. Most public schools rely on the platforms of modular distance learning, and online distance learning is anchored with television-based and radio-based instruction (Malaya, 2020). Remote learning serves those who cannot go and do the classroom teaching, especially in the pandemic. Through distance learning, learning was made possible. It was far way different from a normal class because, in the classroom, motivation and supervision were evident in every class, but in remote learning, learning is self-directed, especially in the off-line classes.

In the K-12 curriculum, students have the right to choose their track and strand when they finish their junior high. During the pandemic, most students chose modular distance learning as their alternative learning delivery modality where they learn from the modules that their teachers prepared. These modules were in accordance with the most essential learning competencies (MELCs) under the Department of Education. These are the most essential competencies under the curriculum, so it needed to have focus. Students' parents were the one who received and retrieved the modules from their schools and they were learning independently on their own learning spaces in their respective houses. Academic support is students' support that motivates them to raise academic success.

The current situation of the Filipino learners made the researcher realize the importance of studying students' assessment on academic support on the modular distance learning during the COVID-19. This study sought to answer the following questions: What is the demographic profile of the students in terms of Socio-Economic Status, Track, and Strand?; How do students assess academic support on the modular distance learning in terms of: Instructional Support, Peer Support, Technical Support, and Parental Support; and Is there a significant difference on students' assessment on modular distance learning when grouped according to students' demographic profile?

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

This study was anchored with the theory of independent learning of the students as it dealt with modular distance learning. It also included the theory on interaction and communication. These theories were the core foundation in this study where students were believed to develop learning by their own with the guidance and support from the people around them as they are not fully capable of understanding all of their lessons and dealing with technical issues on their own. In the interaction model of communication (Schramm, 1997), people alternately send and receive messages and decode them physically or psychologically. This model is applied to the students. At times, they have to decode the messages they received from the support that they got and at times, they had to speak what was in their mind, especially on their modular tasks.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study used descriptive design to obtain information concerning the current status of phenomena to what exists concerning variables or conditions related to this study (Nassaji, 2015) and answer the questions of what, where, when, and how (McCombes, 2019). It was quantitative research. According to Apuke (2017), quantitative research answers how much, where, when, and how many. It also analyses numerical data and uses statistical techniques.

There were two parts in the questionnaire. Part one was the demographic profiling of the students in terms of socioeconomic status, track, and strand that they enrolled. Part two was a self-made 20-item survey questionnaire composed of 20 items. Survey questionnaire was utilized using a 4-point likert scale. The following scoring scale in describing and interpreting the responses of the senior high school student-respondents: 1-strongly agree/highly supported, 2-agree/supported, 3-disagree/not supported, 4-strongly

disagree/poorly supported. These questionnaires were sent to the respondents via e-mail through a google form. After answering the questionnaire, tabulation was done in preparation for the statistical treatment.

Purposive sampling was utilized to identify the respondents. It was done in two (2) Senior High Schools in the Division of Misamis Oriental. There were fifty respondents under this study. These fifty students were not included in the pilot testing where it was participated by forty students.

The study involved a set of survey questionnaires and demographic profiling answered by the senior high student- respondents. The result of the demographic profiling supported the result of the survey questionnaire. The gathered answers in the questionnaire and demographic profiling were utilized to answer the study's four (3) problems. The researcher did the collection, recording, and tabulation of data and strict confidentiality was observed during the whole process of the study. In measuring the demographic profile of the respondents, frequency and percentage were utilized. In measuring whether there is a significant difference in the academic support on the modular distance learning of the students during COVID-19 when grouped according to their demographic profile, the researcher used one-way ANOVA. Tables were then used in describing the students' assessment. This research was conducted for 2 months.

The survey questionnaire utilized was self-made and underwent CVI (Content Validity Index) and FVI (face validity index) calculations (Yusoff, 2019). Validators were composed of four master teachers and two principals from the district where the research was done and the result of the CVI and FVI was 0.85 which showed a satisfactory level of response process validity for the questionnaire. It also underwent pilot testing to 40 senior high students. The result of the reliability testing of the pilot testing was .80 (Cronbach's Alpha) which showed a high level of reliability. After the validation and pilot testing, the researcher floated the instrument to 50 senior high students.

Through written request, the researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Misamis Oriental to gather data from the schools under this research. Upon approval, the researcher proceeded to the school heads of the two (2) senior high schools to ask permission to conduct the study in their school. The researcher allowed the parents to sign a letter of consent and a permit to the students that they will be the respondents for this research. The researcher sent the questionnaires to the students via e-mail in coordination with their class adviser. The objectives of the research were stated to the respondents. It was explained to them that the questionnaire was for the purpose of this research and that the data gathered will be of full confidentiality and will be solely used for this research. The researcher retrieved their answers via google form.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The following tables showed problem number one on the demographic profile of the senior high school students in terms of Socio-Economic Status; Track; and Strand.

The demographic profile plays a significant role in research. It would give an idea to the researcher as to the profile status of the respondents. It is essential to determine whether the individual participants are qualified to represent a sample of the population.

Students' socio-economic status has always been an issue, especially to students who belong to the poverty line. Students who belong to the poverty line may come to school starving and may not focus well on the discussion. As a result, the student would get a low grade and may not be satisfied in going to school.

The economic class where the students belonged is according to the Philippine Institute for Development Studies data to measure their socioeconomic status from the monthly income of their parents or guardian.

Table 1. The Demographic profile of Students in Terms of Socio-Economic Status

Parents' Salary per Month	Frquency	Percentage
Less than PHP 10,481	19	38%
Between PHP 10,481 and PHP 20,962	28	56%
Between PHP 20,962 and PHP 41,924	3	6%
Between PHP 41,924 and PHP 73,367	0	0%
Between PHP 73,367 and PHP 125,772	0	0%
Between PHP 125,772 and PHP 209,620	0	0%
PHP 209,620 and above	0	0%
TOTAL	50	100%

Legend:Less than PHP 10,481-Poor; between PHP 10,481 and PHP 20,962-Low Income Class; between PHP 20,962 and PHP 41,924-Lower Middle Income Class; between PHP 41,924 and PHP 73,367-Middle Middle-Income Class; between PHP 73,367 and PHP 125,772-Upper Middle-Income Class; between PHP 125,772 and PHP 209,620-Upper-Income Class; and between PHP 125,772 and PHP 209,620-Rich

Table 1 shows that most of the respondents' socioeconomic status mostly belonged to low income class where 56% of them belonged to this class. Only 6% of them belonged to lower middle income class. Though 6% of the repondents belonged to lower middle income class, the parents or guardians of the respondents mostly were minimum wage earners.

The school site is in a rural area and the cost of living is not high so as the parents' salary. This is why no respondents belong to middle-middle income,upper income, and rich. Students whose parents earning PhP 41,924 and above were rare to find in these schools also considering that it was a public school.

This finding is supported with the study of Agullana et al. (2017) that most of the students in the public school belong to the low-income class. Further, the author explains in their findings that the demographic profile of the students had an impact on their learning, especially when it comes to school requirements that parents cannot afford to pay. Projects and activities that need materials that parents cannot buy affects the learning and grade of the student.

Regardless of their socio-economic status, senior high school students have the right to choose their track and strand after finishing junior high. Under the track are the Academic Track, Technical-Vocational Livelihood (TVL) Track, Sports Track, and the Arts and Design Track. The academic track is for those who wish to pursue college. On the other hand, the Technical Vocational Livelihood track is for the students who want to hone their skills for future employment right after finishing senior high. Sports track is for students who want to gain more skills and knowledge on physical education and other recreational activities. The arts and Design track are for the students who wish to go to creative industries for in this track, their artistic skills will be developed.

Table 2. The Demographic Profile of Students in Terms of Track

Track	Frequency	Percentage
Academic Track	20	40%
Technical-Vocational and Livelihood (TVL) Track	30	60%
Sports Track	0	0%
Arts and Design Track	0	0%
TOTAL	50	100%

As can be gleaned from Table 2, 60% of the respondents were under the Technical-Vocational and Livelihood (TVL) track. Most of the respondents belonged to TVL track because one of the schools under this study is a national agricultural high school. There were 40% who were under the academic track. None of the respondents were under the sports and arts and design track as most of the students even in their enrollment belonged to the two tracks because the schools did not offer these tracks. According to ADB Knowledge Events (2019), the main constrain that many SHS does not offer this track is because of the insufficiency of the specialized teachers. This insufficiency needs to be addressed to cater the students who wish to enroll in the said tracks.

Students who wished to enroll in sports and arts and design track under the district had to go to another district that offered these tracks. Moreover, insufficiency and lack of interested enrollees were the reasons why it was not offered in the schools under this study. Students preferred to enroll in a track that had practical skills where they had the chance to earn a national certificate and enabled them to have a work right after finishing senior high.

In the study conducted by Malonda (2017), the Academic track was still the most chosen track of the student followed by TVL track. Sports track and arts and design track were the least chosen by the students. However, the most preferred tracks by the students vary from one place to another. In this study, TVL was preferred by the respondents considering that these students wants to live a practical life.

The Academic Track have four strands, namely, Accountancy, Business and Management (ABM); Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS); Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics (STEM); and General Academic Strand (GAS). The Technical-Vocational Livelihood (TVL) Track has also four strands, namely, Home Economics (HE); Information and Communicaton Technology (ICT); Agri-Fishery Arts (AFA), and Industrial Arts (IA). The following table presents the strand that the respondents took up.

The ABM strand focuses on corporate operations and it is mainly on the topic of business. STEM on the other hand is focused on the more advanced concept of science, mathematics, and technology. GAS is for students who are still undecided about what track they should take, while HE is a strand for students who want to gain national certificates for their skills. ICT is for students who are fond of technology. AFA is a strand for students who want to have hands-on activities to develop their agriculture and aquaculture skills. The IA is for students who wish to hone their plumbing, welding, driving, and electronic repairs.

Table 3. The Demographic profile of Students in Terms of Strand

Strand	Frequency	Percentage
Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM)	6	12%
Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS)	4	8%
Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics (STEM)	6	12%
General Academic Strand (GAS)	4	8%
Home Economics (HE)	17	34%
Information and Communications Technology (ICT)	2	4%
Agri-Fishery Arts (AFA)	7	14%
Industrial Arts (IA)	4	8%
TOTAL	50	100%

It was evident in Table 3 that Home Economics (HE) was the strand that most of the respondents took up (percentage:34%) while Information and Communication Technology (ICT) had least enrollees (percentage:4%). Considering the national agricultural high school as one of the schools under this study, most of the respondents were under this strand. Information Communication and Technology had the least enrollees

from the respondents because there were few enrolles in the said strand. Respondents who were under this strand belonged to lower middle income class. During the pandemic, enrollees in the said strand was low. Perhaps it did not only restrict students from going to school, but were also restricted from using school facilities from the school as it was necessary for students under this strand to have their own gadgets.

There were 14% who were under the Agri-Fishery Arts strand which was also the second in rank to the most enrolled strand. The choice of strand is on the students' choice. Top chosen strand always depends on a particular area. According to the study of Moneva & Mablás (2019), factors that SHS students choose their strand are socio-economic status and peer influence. At times, students enroll in a particular strand because it was where their peers were enrolling or it was what their parents told them to enroll because of financial constraints. These were just some of the factors why students enrolled in such strand. In other schools, like the tracks, there were still strands that were not offered because of fewer enrollees and lack of school buildings and facilities.

The following tables answer problem number two on students' assessment on academic support in terms of Instructional Support; Peer Support; Technical Support; and Parental Support.

The academic support that a student received is not the same with the other students. Instructional support is the support that they received from their teachers. Senior high school teachers were departmentalized, but the classroom adviser was their main source of information from all their queries regarding the lessons indicated in their modules.

Table 4. Mean Distribution Of Students' Assessment on Instructional Support

Indicator	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. I know what I was expected to accomplish every week.	1.80	1.09	Agree	Supported
2. I feel that I could ask questions to my teachers regarding the lessons.	2.48	1.16	Agree	Supported
3. The teachers encourage me to regularly submit my written and performance tasks.	1.36	0.60	Strongly Agree	Highly Supported
4. The teachers give feedback to my performances.	1.20	0.53	Strongly Agree	Highly Supported
5. I am encouraged by my teachers to inquire on topics that I am having difficulty with.	1.58	0.95	Strongly Agree	Highly Supported
6. I have a good communication with my teachers.	2.04	1.12	Agree	Supported
7. The teachers always update me on school activities.	1.68	1.13	Strongly Agree	Highly Supported
OVERALL	1.74	0.94	Strongly Agree	Highly Supported

Legend: 3.26-4.00-Strongly Disagree; 2.6-3.25-Disagree; 1.76-2.5-Agree; 1.00-1.75-Strongly Agree

Table 4 emphasized that respondents were highly supported on the instructional support they received, as evident in their assessment. It had an overall mean of 1.74. The teachers gave feedback to their performances with the lowest mean (1.20) while asking questions to their teachers regarding the lessons received the highest mean (2.48). Furthermore, the result showed that the respondents were grateful for how their teachers handled them while they were learning in their own learning spaces. Open communication to teachers and students were necessary especially during the modular distance learning. There were topics that students had difficulty with and the closest resources they had are the teachers. Through communication, teachers can still teach the students even without discussing the topics face-to-face, and teachers can easily monitor the students' learning progress. Despite teachers handled their major subjects, still the advisers were the main contact person of the students as they were the ones who organized the whole class.

Subsequently, Cottingham (2020) suggested developing a curriculum and resources to guide the students while they are on a distance learning. It is a difficult job since students and teachers were on the process

of the new normal of education, but teachers' curriculum and resources were necessary to be guided in delivering quality education to all students.

Furthermore, it was emphasized that learners' overall assessment with the instructional support from their teachers were the result of teachers' effort to update and monitor their students even if they were not in the school premises. Giving extra time and effort to the students was one of these teachers' concerns to keep the students monitored.

Peer support is the support that they got from their classmates on collaborative activities since group activities were present during the distance learning. The engagement has been present during face-to-face classes and even during the time of the pandemic. MELCs in the senior high included social skills. This is why activities involving discussion, brainstorming, and other peer activities, whether pair or group were present even in remote learning.

Table 5. Mean Distribution Of Students' Assessment on Peer Support

Indicator	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. There were many opportunities to have an interaction with peers through performance tasks.	2.02	1.15	Agree	Supported
2. Group discussions are present in group activities.	2.38	1.03	Agree	Supported
3. My peers are supportive and participative on the group tasks.	2.00	1.12	Agree	Supported
4. I always support my peers as I am also supported by them.	1.36	0.60	Strongly Agree	Highly Supported
OVERALL	1.96	0.98	Strongly Agree	Highly Supported

Legend: 3.26-4.00-Strongly Disagree;2.6-3.25-Disagree;1.76-2.5-Agree;1.00-1.75-Strongly Agree

Table 5 presented that respondents least responded that they strongly agreed that they support their peers as they supported them as it had a mean of 1.36. The respondents mostly agreed that group discussions were present in group activities as it had a mean of 2.38. Group activities were encouraged to schools to continue developing their interpersonal skills and still have communication not just with their teachers, but also with their classmates though they were far from each other.

Under the modular distance learning includes tasks that can be done individually, by pair, or by group. It was designed to allow students to cope up with their classmates and discuss topics relevant to their lessons. Through these activities, self-confidence and social skills were met. Support system on peers were present under this study. It was evident that as group activities were active, the students were also on completing their group tasks.

The findings were supported by Ivone et al. (2020) who espoused group activity to be present in the distance learning even if it was a challenging task as it was believed that it was most effective in a classroom setting. Since remote learning was learning in their respective houses, group works were also necessary to have an engagement with their classmates. It also made communication stronger among the students.

The overall mean of 1.96 showed that respondents strongly agreed with the support that they received from their peers. Peer support impacted the respondents with the initiative of the teachers to have group activities even if the students were learning in their respective learning spaces.

Technical Support measures the support that students received from their sources especially when they had troubles on their gadgets and internet connection on doing their modular tasks that needed gadgets and internet connectivity. Though the respondents were under modular distance learning, they needed internet connectivity and gadgets for some of their subjects' activities.

Table 6. Mean Distribution Of Students' Assessment on Technical Support

Indicator	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. I know where to go in case of technical issues on my gadgets.	2.76	1.04	Disagree	Not Supported
2. I feel like I could overcome technical issues.	2.38	1.03	Agree	Supported
3. I know whom to ask help for technical support.	2.46	1.09	Agree	Supported
4. I feel like I have enough resources for technical assistance.	2.70	1.28	Disagree	Not Supported
OVERALL	2.61	1.11	Disagree	Not Supported

Legend: 3.26-4.00-Strongly Disagree;2.6-3.25-Disagree;1.76-2.5-Agree;1.00-1.75-Strongly Agree

Table 6 showed that the respondents least agreed that they know whom to ask help for technical support (mean:2.38) and most respondents disagreed that they know where to go in case of technical issue (mean:2.76). Since the area had less resources on technology, the technical support had been a struggle to high school students.

The overall mean of 2.61 emphasized that respondents were not supported with the technical support they received. It also showed that they had difficulty with the resources for technical assistance. Moreover, students had no enough resources for technical support especially on areas that are not highly urbanized. However, This struggle was present to SHS students even before the pandemic. They also did not know how to handle technical issues on their own gadgets. Technical issues were inevitable especially that they always use their gadgets for personal and academic purposes. Despite the inevitable issues, their resources were lacking. They did not have enough knowledge to fix the issues as they did have all the fixing tools needed. They also did not know many people to call to respond to their problem on technicalities.

According to the study of Cruz (2021), technical issues had been a problem for SHS students and made learning more difficult. This was why respondents were dissatisfied with the technical support they got. Teachers should also assist students who needed technical assistance and increase their media literacy (Alvarez, 2021). Teachers who were knowledgeable on fixing technicalities are big help to students. In this way, they can give support to the students on technical issues.

Parental Support measures the support that students received from their parents while answering their modules. Parents' always play a great role in the students' learning process. In the time of the pandemic, their tasks had been doubled especially that they still need to guide and teach their children at home. At the same time, they were the ones who submitted and retrieved the modules of their children to school. Parents were challenged especially those who had many children to monitor.

Table 7. Mean Distribution Of Students' Assessment on Parental Support

Indicator	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. My parents guide me in my lessons.	2.48	1.11	Agree	Supported
2. I know when to ask parental assistance	2.00	1.12	Agree	Supported
3. I feel comfortable asking assistance to my parents whenever I needed their assistance.	2.44	1.09	Agree	Supported
4. My parents know all of the lessons that I take every day.	2.86	0.99	Disagree	Not Supported
5. I am provided with all the materials I need on my written and performance tasks.	2.92	0.94	Disagree	Not Supported
OVERALL	2.55	1.05	Disagree	Not Supported

Legend: 3.26-4.00-Strongly Disagree;2.6-3.25-Disagree;1.76-2.5-Agree;1.00-1.75-Strongly Agree

Table 7 presented an overall mean of 2.55 for parental support, which means they were not supported. It showed that respondents least agreed that they know when to ask parental assistance (mean:2.00), but mostly disagreed that they were provided with all the materials they needed on their written and performance tasks (mean:2.92). The pandemic did not only bring school closure, but also workers lost their work. Parents who were minimum wage earners and had many children to feed had difficulty producing materials that their children needed. If they struggle for food, how much more for school supplies. Students disagreed that they get full support from their parents, especially during the pandemic.

Agaton et al. (2021) emphasized on their study the experiences of the parents on the remote learning. It was stated that parents also were struggling with their children's lessons and they also had financial problems that caused the learners to feel unsupported by them. In the PISA 2015 result, students whose parents were supportive to their children were more motivated and competitive compared to those who were not. Gemechu (2018) emphasized that parents affect the student's learning status by being their support system. The support that they received from them had a huge impact in their learning process.

Moreover, parents who are hands on to their children were well updated with the activities of their children. They were also known to the school activities and they know what their children needed to achieve better understanding on the lessons despite that they are not physically present in school.

To answer problem number three whether there is a significant difference in students' assessment of academic support when grouped according to demographic profile, one-way ANOVA was used as statistical treatment.

The following tables indicate the result of the statistical data showing the interplay of students' assessment on academic support according to their demographic profile as to Instructional Support, Peer Support, Technical Support, and Parental Support. Their assessment on instructional support measured H_0 in this study that there is no significant difference on students' assessment on instructional support when grouped according to their demographic profile.

Table 8. Significant Difference Of Students' Assessment on Instructional Support When Grouped According To Students' Demographic Profile

Demographic Profile	Instructional Support			
	f-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Socio-Economic Status	5.785	.006	Reject H_0	Significant
Track	3.341	.074	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Strand	3.970	.002	Reject H_0	Significant

As can be gleaned from table 8, the p-value of the students' satisfaction according to their socio-economic status was .006 and according to their strand was .002. Since it was lower than .05, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference on the students' assessment on instructional support according to their socio-economic status and strand. The track to where the students were under had no significant difference since its p-value is .074. This result manifests that the track of the students made no difference when it comes to the instructional support they received while they were on modular distance learning.

Socioeconomic status plays a significant role in students' learning process (Thomson, 2018). Students from different socioeconomic statuses had different views on the support they received from their teachers. One may agree that he is strongly supported, while the other would assess it as only supported. Just like the strand. Since the respondents were enrolled in different strand, they also assess differently their teachers as to the support given to them during the modular distance learning.

This finding was supported by the study of Foerderer et al. (2021) that instructional support is the most significant predictor in students' satisfaction and that satisfaction varies from one student to the other. Moreover, teachers' availability is essential in keeping the students on track with the lessons and keep them monitored even

if they were far from their students. Answering questions from students also motivated them to answer their activities correctly for the whole week.

According to their demographic profile, students' assessment of peer support is how students assess the support they received from their peers and the significant difference that it had with their demographic profile. Using one-way ANOVA, it measured H_02 in this study that there is no significant difference in students' peer support assessment when grouped according to their demographic profile.

Table 9. Significant Difference Students' Assessment on Peer Support When Grouped According To Students' Demographic Profile

Demographic Profile	Peer Support			
	f-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Socio-Economic Status	8.480	.001	Reject H_0	Significant
Track	9.324	.004	Reject H_0	Significant
Strand	2.128	.061	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 9 presented the socioeconomic status of the students had .001 p-value and track has .004 p-value. This shows that both variables had a significant difference in their assessment with the support they received from their peers. It also emphasized that the strand of the student-respondents had no significant difference on their assessment on peer support since its p-value was .061.

Peer or group support was much needed by senior high students, especially when they had group activities. Everyone's participation was much appreciated during the MDL because they had their learning spaces, but they also had to do group works. Remote learning was a struggle, but interaction and teamwork were enhanced. The strand had no significant difference because regardless of the strand they were, aside from speaking, they were also able to hear others' ideas. They were able to practice their right to hear and the right to be heard.

According to Brame&Biel (2015), working in groups enables the students to hear their peers and at somepoint, to speak. Founded by the theory of constructivism, group activities are essential in developing good communication among the students and enhancing interdependency and creativity. Distance learning bought by COVID-19 did not hinder group activities and in fact, teachers consider such activity for their performance tasks in every quarter.

Students' assessment of technical support according to their demographic profile is how students measure the technical support they received from their sources and the significant difference it had with their demographic profile. Using one-way ANOVA, it measured H_03 in this study that there is no significant difference in students' peer support assessment when grouped according to their demographic profile.

Table 10. Significant Difference Of Students' Assessment on Technical Support When Grouped According To Students' Demographic Profile

Demographic Profile	Technical Support			
	f-value	p-value	Description	Interpretation
Socio-Economic Status	2.40	.102	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Track	3.818	.057	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Strand	1.698	.136	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 10 showed that in the demographic profile of the students, the result on students'assessment on technical support is not significant since the p-value of socioeconomic status is .102; track is .057; and strand is 136. It manifests that their demographic profile had no difference in their learning satisfaction in this aspect in their socio economic status, track and strand.

Regardless of students' demographic profile, technical issues were a great dilemma that students faced while learning under the MDL. They did not have enough knowledge on it, and so are the people around them. Aside from that, they don't have enough resources to deal with the technical they encountered.

In the study conducted by Ozudogru (2021), almost all students were not supported when it comes to technicalities. Students in some areas had slow internet connection. Online activities were not completed due to this. Some students do not have phones suitable for connecting to the internet. However, despite their profile, there was no difference on their assessment. They mostly were not supported as they had technical struggles.

According to their demographic profile, the respondents' assessment of parental support was measured through one-way ANOVA. It measured H_0 in this study where there is no significant difference in students' parental support assessment when grouped according to their demographic profile.

Table 11. Significant Difference Of Students' Assessment on Parental Support When Grouped According To Students' Demographic Profile

Demographic Profile	Parental Support			
	f-value	p-value	Description	Interpretation
Socio-Economic Status	.098	.907	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Track	.306	.583	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Strand	.404	.894	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 11 manifests that there was no significant difference in the learning satisfaction of the respondents on parental support when grouped according to their demographic profile since

The p-value of socioeconomic status is .907; track is .583; and strand is .894. The three variables showed that the null hypothesis was accepted. Regardless of their demographic profile, they had no difference in their parental support assessment. They did not get the support they needed from their parents. Parents were the one who should support their children towards academic success. Their support drives the students to study harder, but the lack of support means there was also a lack of drive and motivation. According to ACS International Schools (2021), there was a great call to flexibility and resilience as education shifted from the classroom to houses. Learning remotely was a struggle, and parents' support was a great necessity for the students in their learning progress.

In the study of Bhamani et.al. (2020), they emphasized how parents struggled with distance learning as they also had other works to do aside from teaching and monitoring their children. Nevertheless, they were doing their best to cope up with the struggles. Students who were supported by their parents academically were more motivated and found that they achieve more (Jang & Suh, 2021). In the pandemic where students were learning remotely, parents guidance was much needed by students in all levels.

V. CONCLUSION

Teachers play a vital role in the learning process of the learners. They are held responsible for the learning progress. However, teachers' creativity in motivating, updating, and monitoring the learners was challenged, especially in the pandemic where the students were learning in different learning spaces. This challenge can be resolved through teachers' way of channeling good communication to students through their parents who received and retrieved their children's module.

Further, academic support is vital, especially in the time of the pandemic. Students were learning in their respected houses and their parents and teachers still served as their guide in learning. Accordingly, the challenge on learning during the pandemic was real, but, students were doing their best to learn despite their own learning challenges.

Teachers may establish good communication to the students and to the parents. If parents or any relatives of the learners do not have enough knowledge on a certain topic, learners should be allowed to go to school in case he does not have a gadget for communication provided that teachers will coordinate with the principal and barangay officials for the said learning intervention and follow health protocols;

Administrators should give assistance to the teachers in making learning more possible during distance learning. Enough learning resources should be provided to be utilized by the students; despite the challenges they face, parents should be updated on submitting the modules and should have knowledge on school activities.

For the future researcher to conduct a parallel study that considers other variables on the learning satisfaction of the students on the distance learning.

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